

POLAND

POLAND

ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MODERN PROGRAMS FOR THE PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF DIABETES MELLITUS IN PRIMARY HEALTH CARE SETTINGS

Khomidov Feruz Kasimovich
Abdullayeva Dilafruz Gayratovna

Bukhara State Medical Institute
Tashkent Medical Academy, Uzbekistan

ORCID NO: 0000-0002-0858-4210

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14024568>

Annotation

The study analyzes the effectiveness of modern programs for the prevention and treatment of diabetes mellitus at the primary health care level. With the increasing incidence of type 2 diabetes, the implementation of preventive programs and improving the availability of early diagnosis is becoming an important direction. The work includes an analysis of existing approaches and measures applied in primary care, such as screening, patient education, and digital technologies. The results of the study show that programs focusing on early detection and prevention have a significant impact on reducing morbidity and improving health outcomes in patients at high risk of diabetes.

Key words: diabetes mellitus, primary link, prevention, treatment, efficiency, health care.

Relevance

Diabetes mellitus, especially type 2, is one of the most common and socially significant pathologies in the world. The incidence of diabetes continues to grow, which requires the development and implementation of effective prevention and early diagnosis programs at the primary health care level. This level provides medical care to the majority of patients, which makes it the most important point for implementing preventive measures, early detection of the disease and providing basic treatment.

With insufficient patient awareness of risk factors and the first symptoms of diabetes, educational programs and access to digital health monitoring tools are becoming key areas of focus. These measures can prevent the development of diabetes, reduce the number of complications and improve the quality of life of patients. An analysis of the effectiveness of modern programs implemented at the primary care level makes it possible to identify successful prevention models and implement them to improve the national strategy for combating diabetes.

The aim of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of modern programs for the prevention and treatment of diabetes in primary health care to improve the quality of medical care and reduce the prevalence of the disease.

Materials and methods. Data from outpatient diabetes prevention programs, statistical reports on the incidence rate and indicators of early detection of diabetes among patients were analyzed. Methods included questionnaires of doctors and patients, analysis of digital tools for diabetes control, and evaluation of educational activities. Comparative analysis allowed us to assess the impact of programs on the level of diagnosis and prevention of diabetes and identify successful models applicable in primary care.

Results

The results of the study showed that the introduction of educational programs and digital technologies at the primary health care level can increase patients' awareness of risk factors and diabetes control. A survey of doctors and patients found that more than 70% of respondents considered early diagnosis programs important for preventing diabetes, and 65% noted the positive impact of digital technologies on disease management. Programs that include regular screenings and healthy lifestyle awareness have shown a reduction in the incidence of diabetes complications and morbidity. These results point to the need for widespread adoption of such approaches in the healthcare system.

As our studies have shown, the leading pathological symptoms in patients with diabetes mellitus 2 were stress, sleep disorders and impaired diuresis, which occurred in every 3-4 patients, and weight loss was observed in every fifth patient, muscle weakness in every sixth

Conclusion

Effective diabetes prevention and treatment programs at the primary care level play a key role in reducing the incidence and improving the quality of care. The results of the study confirm that screening activities, educational programs and digital tools allow patients to identify risks and monitor their health in time, preventing complications of diabetes. Regular public awareness activities on prevention and early diagnosis contribute to raising awareness and improving health outcomes. Optimizing programs and integrating digital technologies at the primary care level is recommended to reduce the burden of diabetes and improve health outcomes in the country.

References:

1. Abdullaeva, D. G., & Ikromova, N. I. (2023). Living Well: Understanding the Tapestry of Obesity Risks. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences* (2993-2149), 1(10), 480–486. Retrieved from <https://grnjournal.us/index.php/AJPMHS/article/view/2254>
2. Barbarash O. L. et al. Prediabetes as an interdisciplinary problem: definition, risks, approaches to the diagnosis and prevention of type 2 diabetes and cardiovascular complications //Russian Journal of Cardiology. – 2019. – №. 4. – Pp. 83-91.
3. Ergasheva G. T. REDUCING THE RISK OF COMPLICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES AND CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES //Education Science And Innovative Ideas In The World. - 2024. - Vol. 38. - no. 7. - pp. 210-218.
4. Galitskaya S. S., Mokhort T. V., Likhorad N. M. Vozmozhnosti profilaktiki sakharnogo diabeta 2 tipa [Possibilities of prevention of type 2 diabetes]. – 2011. – №. 1. – P. 50-55.
5. Абдуллаева, Д. ., & Ачилова, И. . (2024). ФАКТОРЫ РИСКА ГЕСТАЦИОННОГО САХАРНОГО ДИАБЕТА. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(10), 255–263. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/44513>
6. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13947129

